

Christianity in Tang China

also known as “Luminous Religion”, “Nestorian Christianity”, “Jingjiao 景教”

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Entry tags: Chinese Christian Traditions, Chinese Religion, Religious Group

Christians in Tang China gave a Chinese name for Christianity: Jingjiao 景教, a term translated as “the Luminous Religion/Teaching” or “the Illustrious Religion” or “the Brilliant Teaching”. Not a few scholars regard it as a “Nestorian” Church, a derogatory term used to call the Church of the East or East Syriac Christianity in the Western ecclesiastical traditions (Latin West and Greek East). The degree to which the Church of the East has to do with the Archbishop of Constantinople, Nestorius, who was condemned as a heresiarch during the Council of Ephesus (431), is a point that has been re-examined by a few patristic scholars. With the help of newly-discovered materials in Syriac, scholars such as James F. Bethune-Baker, Robert V. Sellers, Aloys Grillmeier, and Sebastian P. Brock began to question this ingrained preconception from the Western perspective. Scholars like Brock emphasize that the Syriac tradition, of which the Church of the East is a part, has a much earlier history than the so-called Nestorianism. The story of Christianity in Tang China begins in 635 with the coming of Aluoben 阿羅本, a Persian波斯/Daqin大秦 monk who introduced his religion in front of the second emperor of the dynasty and paved the way for the spread of Christianity in the confines of the Tang empire. This story is recorded on the famous Christian stele discovered at Xi'an in 1623/5. The text of the inscription was composed by Jingjing 景淨, who was a priest and charespiscopus of China. The stone was set in place in 781 probably in or near the Jingjiao temple in the imperial capital Chang'an (today's Xi'an). It proffers a brief history of Jingjiao in 146 years, which arguably echoes the rise and decline of the Tang empire. The presence of Jingjiao in the Tang period was also evidenced by Chinese official records, such as Tang Huiyao 唐會要 (Institutional History of Tang), and other Chinese documents by Buddhists or Daoists. The history of Jingjiao came to an end with the issue of the edict of 845, which initiated the persecution of Buddhism as well as other foreign religions including Daqin Jingjiao. However, historical documents of the 9th and 10th centuries mentioned that a few Jingjiao Christians still survived in China after 845. In the 20th and 21st centuries, more documents and archaeological discoveries (like tomb epitaphs) have been found, especially at Dunhuang's Hidden Library. These documents not only confirm the authenticity of the stele but also enrich our knowledge of Jingjiao. The understanding of Jingjiao and the community of Jingjiao Christians, as shown in this entry, is built on the Xi'an inscription and these manuscripts, despite being fragmentary. These Jingjiao documents include Xuting Mishisuo jing 序聽迷詩所經 (“Book of Jesus-Messiah” or “Book of listening to the Messiah”), Yishen lun 一神論 (“Discourse on the One God”), Da Qin Jingjiao Sanwei mengdu zan 大秦景教三威蒙度讚 (“Hymn in adoration of the Three Persons and of salvation”), Zunjing 尊經 (“Book of Veneration”), Zhixuan anle jing 志玄安樂經 (“Book on attaining mysterious serenity and joy”), Da Qin Jingjiao Xuanyuan zhiben jing 大秦景教宣元至本經 (“Book of the proclamation of the highest origin of origins”), as well as Da Qin Jingjiao Dasheng tongzhen guifa zan 大秦景教大聖通真歸法讚 (“Hymn of praise for Great Holiness, attaining the truth, and returning to the dharma”). In front of the stele and other Jingjiao documents, there was a community of Jingjiao Christians, who were mostly migrants of Iranian origin and spoke Persian or Sogdian. The bilingual (Chinese-Syriac) stele itself tells of their hybrid identity. On the one hand, Jingjiao was linked with the Church of the East in the Middle East. Syriac played a significant role in the theology and liturgy of Jingjiao. The hierarchy of the Church of the East is indicated on the Xi'an stele: both Chinese and Syriac names of the Catholicos Henanisho were engraved on the stele. On the other hand, the text engaged with the historical and religious contexts of Tang China by employing a few terminologies of the pre-existing Three Religions/Teachings (sanjiao, 三教), such as Confucianism, Buddhism, and Daoism. This was the first attempt at transmitting the Christian ideas, such as Christology and the Trinity, in the Chinese language, more specifically in Middle Chinese. In the Jingjiao corpus, introducing the idea of the Only God, who Jesus

Christ is, what the Messiah teaches were some major tasks of Jingjiao Christians.

Date Range: 618 CE - 906 CE

Region: Tang China (c. 700 CE)

Region tags: East Asia, China, Central Asia, Chang'an, China, Xi'an 西安, Luoyang, Dunhuang

The borders of Tang China are distinct from those of the People's Republic of China. Geographically, the movement of Jingjiao was linked with the so-called Silk Roads. Chang'an, Luoyang, and Dunhuang are three places where the majority of documents and archaeological materials have been discovered.

Status of Participants:

- ✓ Elite
- ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Luo Xianglin. *Tangyuan erdai zhi Jingjiao*. Hong Kong: Zhongguo xueshe, 1966.
- Source 2: Zhu Qianzhi, *Zhongguo Jingjiao*. Beijing: Renmin Chubanshe, 1993.
- Source 3: Lin, Wushu. *Tangdai Jingjiao zaiyanjiu*. Beijing: Zhongguo shehui kexue chubanshe, 2003.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 635 CE - 845 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

- Source 1: Havret, Henri. *La stèle chrétienne de Si-ngan-fou*. Chang-hai: Imprimerie de la mission catholique, 1895.
- Source 2: Pelliot, Paul, and Antonino Forte. *L'inscription nestorienne de Si-ngan-fou*. Kyoto: Scuola di studi sull'Asia orientale, 1996.
- Source 3: Legge, James. *The Nestorian Monument of Hsī-an Fû in Shen-Hsī, China*. London: Trübner & Co., 1888.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 635 CE - 845 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

- Source 1: Latourette, Kenneth Scott. *A History of Christian Missions in China*. London, 1929.
- Source 2: Moule, A. C. (Arthur Christopher). *Christians in China before the Year 1550*. London: Society for Promoting Christian Knowledge, 1930.
- Source 3: Moffett, Samuel Hugh. *A History of Christianity in Asia, Volume I: Beginnings to 1500*. Maryknoll, New York: Orbis Books, 1998.

Notes: Christianity in the Tang dynasty has always been one of the first chapters in many books on the history of Christianity in China or Asia. There are more studies focusing on individual texts of Jingjiao. See the bibliography section below.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 635 CE - 845 CE

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

– Source 1: Saeki, Yoshirō. *The Nestorian Documents and Relics in China*. Tokyo: Toho Bunkwa Gakuin: Academy of Oriental Culture, Tokyo Institute, 1951.

– Source 2: Tang, Li. *A study of the history of Nestorian Christianity in China and its literature in Chinese*. Frankfurt am Main; Oxford: Peter Lang, 2004.

– Source 3: Ferreira, Johan. *Early Chinese Christianity: the Tang Christian Monument and Other Documents*. Strathfield, NSW: St Pauls, 2014.

– Source 1: Weng Shaojun, ed. *Hanyu Jingjiao wendian quanshi [Sino-Nestorian Documents: Commentary and Exegesis]*. Hong Kong: Institute of Sino-Christian Studies, 1995.

– Source 2: Wu Chang Shing, ed. *Daqin Jingjiao zhongguo bei: Daqin Jingjiao wenxian shiyi [Da Qin Jingjiao Liuxing Zhongguo Bei (The Xi'an Stele): Text Analyses with Commentaries on Documents of Da Qin Jingjiao]*. Xinbei: Olive Publishing, 2015.

– Source 3: Wang Lanping. *Tangdai Dunhuang hanwen Jingjiao xiejing yanjiu [Study on Dunhuang Jingjiao Manuscripts of the Tang Dynasty]*. Beijing: Minzu chubanshe, 2016.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: <https://youtu.be/qhdLKBKNf0I>

– Source 1 Description: An illustration of the 'Nestorian' Monument in China by Martin Palmer

– Source 2 URL: https://en.wikipedia.org/w/index.php?title=Church_of_the_East_in_China&oldid=1023838762

– Source 2 Description: Church of the East in China

– Source 3 URL: https://en.wikipedia.org/w/index.php?title=Jingjiao_Documents&oldid=1007989114

– Source 3 Description: Jingjiao Documents

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

– Source 1 URL: https://en.wikipedia.org/w/index.php?title=Xi%27an_Steale&oldid=1023731097

– Source 1 Description: Xi'an Stele

– Source 2 URL: <https://www.bbc.co.uk/programmes/b00p315t>

– Source 2 Description: On the Silk Road (In Our Time) by BBC

– Source 3 URL: <https://youtu.be/0jR3I4ZHRp4>

– Source 3 Description: Dunhuang as Nexus of the Silk Road during the Middle Ages by Victor H. Mair

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

– Source 1 URL: <http://epapers.bham.ac.uk/755/>

– Source 1 Description: The Nestorian Stele published by the Orchard Learning Resources Centre in the University of Birmingham

– Source 2 URL: https://www.mq.edu.au/__data/assets/pdf_file/0007/55987/Xian-Nestorian-Monument-27-07-2016.pdf

– Source 2 Description: Stele on the diffusion of the Luminous Religion of Da Qin (Rome) in the Middle Kingdom Translated by Dr L. Eccles and Prof. Sam Lieu of the SERICA Team in 2016

– Source 3 URL: <https://gallica.bnf.fr/ark:/12148/btv1b8303183c>

– Source 3 Description: Pelliot chinois 3847

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

– Source 1 URL: https://commons.wikimedia.org/w/index.php?title=File:Sutras_on_the_Origin_of_Origins_of_Ta-ch%E2%80%98in_Luminous_Religion_1.jpg&oldid=474911073

– Source 1 Description: Sutras on the Origin of Origins of Ta-ch'in Luminous Religion On the Luoyang Pillar

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is the cultural contact competitive:

– Yes

Notes: Scholars such as Matteo Nicolini-Zani doubt the possibility of the surviving materials revealing Jingjiao's approach to other religions. However, it should be noted that as one of the religions on the Silk Roads, Jingjiao encountered Judaism, Zoroastrianism, Manichaeism, Buddhism, Islam, and, probably, other 'minor' religious traditions such as Shamanism. Besides, Confucianism and Daoism were Chinese indigenous religious traditions with which Jingjiao engaged in the Tang empire. Furthermore, according to records on the Xi'an stele, there were debates between Jingjiao Christians and Buddhists during the period of Empress Wu. But the content of those debates was uncertain. Dunhuang documents do not explicitly mention any controversies with the pre-existing so-called Three Teachings ('sanjiao' 三教), such as Confucianism ('ru' 儒), Buddhism ('shi' 釋), and Daoism ('dao' 道). However, arguments against idolatry are obvious in both the 'Book of Jesus-Messiah' or 'Book of listening to the Messiah' (Xuting mishisuo jing 序聽迷詩所經) and 'Discourse on the One God' (Yishen lun 一神論).

Reference: Matteo Nicolini-Zani. Christian Approaches to Religious Diversity in Premodern China. (P. Schmidt-Leukel undefined, J. Gentz undefined), *Religious Diversity in Chinese Thought*. Springer. isbn: 9781137318503. p.99-100

Reference: Max Deeg. *Along the Silk Road: From Aleppo to Chang'an*. (Josef Lossl , Nicholas Baker-Brian J., Ed.), *A Companion to Religion in Late Antiquity*. John Wiley & Sons.

Reference: Richard Foltz undefined. *Religions of the Silk Road*. Basingstoke: Macmillan. isbn:

9780333946749.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Yes

Notes: Jingjiao engaged with terminologies and thoughts of the Three Teachings ('sanjiao') in various ways. To what degree Jingjiao incorporates sources in these religious traditions has been a question of debate. Scholars such as Samuel Hugh Moffett says that Christianity in the Tang dynasty was 'neither heretically Nestorian nor fatally syncretistic'. However, Martin Palmer famously designates it as 'Taoist Christianity'. It is worth noting that Jingjing/Adam, the author of the Xi'an inscription, once cooperated with the Buddhist monk Prajñā to translate the Buddhist sutra, the Six Pāramitās Sutra, into Chinese in around 782, as noticed by the Japanese scholar J. Takakusu.

Reference: Junjiro Takakusu. The Name of "Messiah" Found in a Buddhist Book; The Nestorian Missionary Adam, Presbyter, Papas of China, Translating a Buddhist Sūtra. T'oung Pao, 7(5)

Reference: Martin Palmer, Eva Wong. The Jesus Sutras. Wellspring/Ballantine. isbn: 9780345434241.

Reference: Samuel Hugh Moffett. A History of Christianity in Asia, Vol. I. Orbis Books. isbn: 9781608331628.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– No

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Assigned at birth (membership is default for this society):

– Yes

Notes: According to entombed epitaphs that were unearthed in the 20th and 21st centuries, Jingjiao was kept as a family faith among Persian and Sogdian people who lived in the Tang empire for various reasons. Rong Xinjiang argues that some details on Li Su and his wife's entombed epigraphs found at Xi'an in 1980, e.g., 'jing' 景 as one of the characters of the names of his sons, indicate the Christian identity of his family. By researching another epigraph unearthed at Xi'an in 1955, Ge Chengyong also discovered a Sogdian family's connection with the Daqin temple at Chang'an: the younger son of the Sogdian Mi Jifen was a monk/priest at the Daqin temple. More explicitly, the epigraph of the Luoyang pillar discovered in 2006 records families originating from the city-states of Bukhara, Maymurch, and Samarkand and their deep connections with the Daqin temple at Luoyang. Thus, sociologically speaking, it may be said that the religious identity was assigned at birth.

Reference: xinjiang Rong. Yige rushi tangchao de bosi jingjiao jiazu. Zhongguo zhongguo yu wailai wenming. Shanghai: Sanlian shudian. p.238-257

Reference: Chengyong Ge , Matteo Nicolini-Zani. The Christian Faith of a Sogdian Family in Chang'an During the Tang Dynasty. p.181-196

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Assigned by personal choice:

– Yes

Notes: No existing texts of Tang China tell of a story of individual conversion. Most key actors in Jingjiao were descendants of the Persian and the Sogdian. Chinese converts can hardly be identified according to these materials. However, the Discourse on the One God and the Book of Jesus-Messiah in the apologetical tone argues for giving up idolatry in varied cults and converting to the worship of the One God.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Assigned by class:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Assigned at a specific age:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Assigned by gender:

– No

Notes: For example, the Luoyang pillar, on which the text of the Book of Proclamation of the highest Origin of Origins was inscribed, was erected beside or in the tomb of the deceased mother, the lady of the An from Bukhara.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Assigned by participation in a particular ritual:

– Yes

Notes: The traditional ritual of initiation in the Church of the East in the Middle East consisted of two parts: the anointing of oil and baptism in water. In the 7th century, post-baptismal anointing and communion were added to the older sequence during the reform of baptismal office under the rule of Catholicos Ishoyahb III. Baptism symbolized the Christian second birth, freeing one from all sins. In the Church of the East, baptism was granted particularly to young adults. However, in later periods, especially under the Islamic rule, politically and ecclesiastically isolated situations made open adult conversions impossible, the baptism of infants and young children becoming the only practice. Baptism by water and spirit is referred to in the Jingjiao inscription: 'fayu shuifeng' 法浴水風, meaning 'His law is to bathe, and the water has a spiritual effect'. Moreover, in narrating the life of Jesus in the Discourse on the One God, the idea of baptism as rebirth was introduced in the translation of Matthew 28: 19, where Jesus asked the eleven disciples to go and make disciples of all nations and to baptize them in [the name of] the Father and of the Son and of the Holy Spirit (Pure Wind).

Reference: Michael Birnie J.. Baptism, Confirmation and Eucharist in the Church of the East. (Johann Marte , Gerhard Wilflinger, Ed.), Syriac Dialogue. Vienna: Pro Oriente. p.67-77

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Assigned by some other factor:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– Yes

Notes: The Church of the East was well-known for its large geographical scale of the mission field, which started from Edessa and the Persian Gulf (Seleucia-Ctesiphon and Bagdad) in the Middle East and extended along the Silk Roads to India and Central Asia and then to East Asia. Although they remained a minority in most of these places, missionaries were zealous in overcoming the geographic, linguistic, and cultural barriers. Meanwhile, the Christian faith also traveled with migrants like traders on the Silk Roads. It is highly likely that missionaries and traders were companions on the Silk Roads. There were also other immigrants who moved to the Chinese empire for various reasons, economic or political. Despite the changes of external circumstances, they still maintained the faith of the family or the tribe as an essential part of their identity. The monastic mission was one of the significant characteristics of the historical expansion of the Church of the East, as emphasized by John Stewart and Steve Cochrane. Monasteries of the Church of the East such as Beit Abhe sent monks and ascetics toward the East including China. The Catholicos Timothy in one of his letters mentioned new missions in Asia: "Many monks cross the sea to India and China with nothing more than a staff and a begging bag." There is no obvious evidence of conversions among the indigenous Chinese population. The Chinese names appearing on the Jingjiao stele do not necessarily indicate the nationality or ethnicity of those Christians. Even if there were any Chinese converts in the Tang dynasty, not enough materials could illustrate their ways of encountering the Christian faith. Although there were some individual Christians who attained high office in Sasanian, Arabic, or Chinese empires, the Church of the East was always removed from the center of political power. These external circumstances precluded East Syriac Christians from any actions of violent proselytism. Western missionaries such as Alfred James Broomhall in China criticized the irenic character of Jingjiao, saying that "their lack of distinctiveness as Christians appears to have led to their annihilation." Bearing the later Catholic and Protestant models of evangelization in mind, David D. Bundy describes the characteristics of the mission of the Church of the East, "The mission of the Nestorian church was not triumphalist, nor did it attach itself to any imperialist or colonialist designs. During the Tang dynasty, the Nestorians came not in a position of strength but as humble monks and traders establishing themselves in China on their own merits unsupported by gunboats, banks, consulates, embassies, or by massive funds. By mission here we understand the extension of Christian faith and ideas and the transmission of that tradition within a cultural context alien to the confession and practice of a Christian community of faith." However, this does not contradict the rhetoric of apology reflected in the texts of Jingjiao.

Reference: David Bundy D. *Missiological Reflections on Nestorian Christianity in China during the Tang Dynasty*. Religion in The Pacific Era. New York: Paragon. p.14-30

Reference: Steve Cochrane. *Many Monks Across the Sea*. isbn: 9781911372950.

Reference: John Stewart. *Nestorian Missionary Enterprise: The Story of a Church on Fire*. Edinburgh: T & T Clark. p.36-49

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for religious professionals:

– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for all adherents:

– I don't know

↳ Is missionary work mandated for religious professionals:

– Yes

↳ Is missionary work mandated for all adherents:

– I don't know

↳ Is proselytization coercive:

– No

Does the religion have official political support

– Yes

Notes: The Xi'an inscription confirms and praises the patronage of emperors. As a text for the public, it particularly describes Jingjiao's relations with the imperial court. The major part of the inscription is not necessarily the ecclesiastical history but the imperial history in which, as the inscription proclaims, Jingjiao played a role and thus prospered. The thread of history is the succession of Tang emperors. The inscription states that Emperor Taizong sent Prime Minister Fang Xuanling to welcome Aluoben in the Western suburb of Chang'an. After reviewing texts of Jingjiao translated by Aluoben, the emperor issued an imperial edict in 638, allowing the spread of Jingjiao in the confines of the Tang empire and the establishment of the Jingjiao temple at the Yining quarter in Chang'an. This edict, though slightly different, is also reproduced and kept in the Chinese official document, Tang Huiyao 唐會要. After the emphasis of the glorious beginning of the religion in China, the inscription continues to tell of the favour and support from Tang emperors in chronological order, though there existed some attacks from Buddhists, especially during the period of Empress Wu who favoured Buddhism. The overwhelming political authority of the Chinese empire over all spheres made it crucial for Jingjiao Christians to obtain permission for the establishment and propagation of Jingjiao from the imperial court. During an earlier period, the support from the Chinese emperor was in part because of the diplomatic relationship with Persia. For instance, the Persian prince Peroz III, or Beilusi 卑路斯, the last Sasanian King of Kings of Iran, took refuge under the Tang court. In 677, he petitioned the Emperor for permission to build a Persian temple in Chang'an, which has been recognized as a Jingjiao temple. Moreover, the Church of the East's elites like some names of figures appearing in the Xi'an inscription were involved in imperial affairs. They were mediators in the Tang court and 'holders and representatives of a post-Sasanian Persian royal and courtly identity'. For instance, as reported in the inscription, the honoree of the stele, Yisi 伊斯, made contributions to suppress the An Lushan Rebellion, which was a disastrous uprising against the ruling of Tang. The government under Emperor Suzong rewarded the community of Jingjiao by allowing them to 'rebuild the Luminous temples in Lingwu and four other commanderies'. The decline of Jingjiao is related to the Huichang Persecution of Buddhism initiated by Emperor Wuzong in 845, which also affected Jingjiao that was recognized as a foreign religion from Daqin. The Old Book of Tang, Jiu Tangshu 舊唐書, describes the consequence of the decree of 845, 'For the monks and nuns who came under the charge of the controllers of aliens making known the religions of foreign countries, they compelled the Ta-Ch'in (Christians) and Mu-hu-fu (Zoroastrians) to the number of more than three thousand persons to return to lay life and to cease to confound the customs of China (Chung hua).'

Reference: R. Todd Godwin. *Persian Christians at the Chinese Court*. Bloomsbury Publishing. isbn: 9781786723161. p.69-101

Reference: Ken-pa Chin. *Jingjiao under the Lenses of Chinese Political Theology*.

Reference: Ian Gilman, Hans-Joachim Klimkeit. Christians in Asia before 1500. Routledge. isbn: 9781136109782. p.271-275

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Are the priests paid by polity:

– I don't know

Notes: The degree to which the Tang government financially support the priesthood is not clear.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Is religious infrastructure paid for by the polity:

– Yes

Notes: The Xi'an stele and some Chinese documents report that Emperor Taizong built a temple for Aluoben at the Yining Quater in Chang'an in the 630s. The imperial court under Emperor Gaozong allowed other temples to be built in other prefectures. It is reasonable to speculate that the imperial government financed the establishment of the Daqin temples.

Reference: A. C. Moule. Christians in China Before the Year 1550. isbn: 9780879688653. p.71

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Are the head of the polity and the head of the religion the same figure:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Are political officials equivalent to religious officials:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Is religious observance enforced by the polity:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Polity legal code is roughly coterminous with religious code:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Polity provides preferential economic treatment (e.g. tax, exemption)

– Yes

Notes: In 845, Emperor Wuzong initiated the Huichang Persecution of Buddhism. The economic reason was significant. As recorded in the Jiu Tangshu, 'these heretical religions must not alone be left when the Buddhists have been suppressed; they must all be compelled to return to lay life and resume their original callings and pay taxes....' This implies that before 845, like Buddhist monks, Jingjiao monks had been exempted from paying taxes.

Reference: Ian Gilman, Hans-Joachim Klimkeit. Christians in Asia before 1500. Routledge. isbn: 9781136109782. p.283

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– Small religious group (one of many small religious groups in sample region)

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: In general, there is a hierarchy in the Church of the East, which includes three orders: episcopate, presbyterate, and diaconate; each order has three divisions. The priesthood was one of the recognized sacraments by Mar Odisho and Patriarch Timothy II. The Syriac tradition claims that Jesus served these nine divisions of the three orders, as indicated in the Biblical narrative. Jingjing or Adam, the author of the Xi'an inscription was titled chorepiscopus, a transcription of the Greek term for "rural bishop". The Catholicos Henanisho's name in both Chinese and Syriac and his title is also engraved on the stone. All this indicates a hierarchical order within Jingjiao.

Reference: David Wilmshurst. *The Ecclesiastical Organisation of the Church of the East, 1318-1913*. Peeters Publishers. isbn: 9789042908765.

Reference: Arthur John Maclean, William Henry Browne. *The Catholicos of the East and His People*. Gorgias PressLlc. isbn: 9781593334031.

Reference: Christoph Baumer. *The Church of the East*. Bloomsbury Publishing. isbn: 9781838609337. p.121

↳ Is there a hierarchy among these leaders:

– Yes

↳ A single leader of a local community:

– Yes

↳ Multiple religious communities each with its own leader, no hierarchy among these leaders:

– No

↳ "Regional" leaders who oversee one or more local leader(s) (e.g. bishops):

– Yes

↳ A single leader for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the sample region:

– Yes

↳ A council or group of leaders for the religious group that oversees all other

leaders in the sample region:

– I don't know

↳ Are leaders believed to possess supernatural powers or qualities:

– I don't know

↳ Are religious leaders chosen:

– Yes

↳ A leader chooses his/her own replacement:

– Yes

↳ A leader's retinue or ministers chooses the new leader:

– I don't know

↳ Other leaders in the religious group choose that leader:

– I don't know

↳ A political leader chooses the leader:

– I don't know

↳ Other members of the leader's congregation choose the leader:

– No

↳ All members of the religious group in the sample region participate in choosing the leader:

– No

↳ Communication with supernatural power(s) believed to be part of the selection process:

– Yes

↳ Are leaders considered fallible:

– I don't know

↳ Are close followers or disciples of a religious leader required to obediently and unquestionably accept the leader's pronouncements on all matters:

– I don't know

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

Notes: The Peshitta, the standard version of the Bible for Syriac Churches, was completed in the early 5th century prior to the Christological controversy. Hence, it has been accepted by both West and East Syriac Churches. According to manuscripts discovered in Central Asia, the Peshitta version played a significant role in this region. It was either directly quoted in the exegetical and liturgical practices or used as the original text of Biblical translations in languages such as Middle Persian, New Persian, and Sogdian. Scripture or 'jing' 經 was a significant term to signal the identity of the religion, which was called scripture-religion of Persia (Bosi jingjiao 波斯經教) as stated in the Chinese official documents. The first activity in which Aluoben engaged was translating scriptures into Chinese. Only after showing Emperor Taizong his translations was Jingjiao allowed to initiate its propagation in Tang China, as recorded in the Xi'an inscription. The two documents that have been attributed to Aluoben, contain a few translations of Biblical verses drawn from the Gospel of Matthew as well as the Acts of the Apostles. Hence, this can be regarded as the earliest attempt at Bible translation into the Chinese language. Another document that was discovered by Paul Pelliot at Dunhuang contains a list of scriptures. The document is titled Zunjing 尊經 or the Book of Veneration. Interestingly, the colophon attached to the text claims that Jingjiao has 530 volumes of scriptures, out of which only 35 scriptures were translated by Jingjing, the author of the Xi'an inscription. Although this is not a biblical canon list, it includes titles of some biblical books, such as Psalms (Duohui shengwang jing 多惠聖王經, Holy King David Scripture), Gospels (A Si Qu Li Rong jing 阿思瞿利容經, The Gospel Scripture), the Pauline Epistles (Baolu fawang jing 寶路法王經, Dharma-King Paul Scripture), and possibly, the Pentateuch (Moushi fawang jing 牟世法王經, Dharma-King Moses Scripture). Unfortunately, no surviving manuscripts of these scriptures have been found.

Reference: . The Oxford Handbook of the Bible in China. New York: Oxford University Press. isbn: 9780190909796. p.47, p.2, p.22

Reference: Mark Dickens. The Syriac Bible in Central Asia. (Erica Hunter D. C.), The Christian Heritage of Iraq. Piscataway: Gorgias Press. isbn: 9781607241119. p.92-120

Reference: Sebastian P. Brock. The Bible in the Syriac Tradition. Gorgias PressLlc. isbn: 9781593333003.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are they written:

– Yes

Notes: Chinese characters and Syriac letters are engraved on the limestone. The text of the Book of Proclamation of the highest Origin of Origins is inscribed on a tombstone in Luoyang and is also written on the scroll manuscript found at Dunhuang. There are other Jingjiao texts are written on different scroll manuscripts.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Are they oral:

– Yes

Notes: It is arguable that the Chinese version of 'Gloria in Excelsis Deo', Hymn in adoration of the Three Persons, was originally sung in a liturgical setting.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– Yes

Notes: The Xi'an inscription claims that the Messiah left 27 volumes of scriptures. Besides, it also says that Aluoben brought 'true scriptures' (zhenjing 真經) into China and translated them in the Chinese imperial court before the permission of the propagation of the religion.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Revealed by a high god:

– Yes

↳ Revealed by other supernatural being:

– No

↳ Inspired by high god:

– Yes

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being:

– No

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings:

– No

↳ Originated from non-divine human being:

– No

↳ Are the scriptures alterable:

– No

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting the scriptures:

– I don't know

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures:

– I don't know

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures:

– No

Notes: The Council of Trent on 8 April 1546 was the first 'ecumenical' council that officially defined the biblical canon and anathematize those who did not accept this ruling. Sebastian Brock says that the canonical lists in the Syriac tradition were not fixed and closed. A form of the flexibility of defining scripture or 'jing' in the Chinese context could be found in the list of books in the Book of Veneration.

Reference: Sebastian P. Brock. *The Bible in the Syriac Tradition*. Gorgias Press LLC. isbn: 9781593333003. p.114-115

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

Notes: The Xi'an stele is the best known monumental religious architecture of Jingjiao that survives. This stele is large, measuring 2.79 meters high, approximately 1 meter wide, and 30 centimeters thick. It was unearthed in 1623/5 and placed in the Chongren-si 崇仁寺 for almost three hundred years. It has been exhibited at Beilin (Forest of Steles, 碑林) Museum at Xi'an since 1907 when a Danish named Frits V. Holm attempted to purchase and remove the original monument for a Western museum. In the 21st century, there are more archaeological discoveries, such as an octagonal pillar, a Christian tomb at Longmen Grottoes, and tomb epitaphs. The octagonal pillar unearthed at Luoyang resembles the Buddhist dhāraṇī pillars, although incomplete, bearing a text of the Book of Proclamation of the highest Origin of Origins, which had been found in a manuscript discovered at Dunhuang. This object is part of the architecture of the tomb of Lady An. It is worth mentioning that more stones with similar crosses and inscriptions dated to the later Yuan dynasty have been found in places such as Beijing and Quanzhou. The octagonal pagoda that belonged to an ancient temple at Zhouzhi 盩厔/周至 was identified by scholars such as Henri Havret and P. Y. Saeki as part of the Jingjiao temple during the Tang dynasty. They believed that this pagoda was originally rebuilt as a Jingjiao temple and in later periods (especially after the persecution of 845) was transformed into a Buddhist temple venerating buddhas and bodhisattvas. The most significant evidence for supporting this view is that this temple's name was Daqin-si according to Chinese materials of the Song and Ming dynasties. Martin Palmer's *The Jesus Sutras* reports his journey of the rediscovery of the pagoda since 1933 when a Chinese scholar, Xiang Da made his journey. This seven-storey pagoda is 38.6 meters tall. The wooden stairs are set inside, reaching the top. However, the Christian identity of the pagoda has also been suspected by Lin Wushu, who argues that the coincidence of using the same name cannot be a solid foundation for

this view. Furthermore, it should be noted that Palmer's imaginative comparison between a hardly-identified sculpture in the pagoda and the icon of Mary giving birth to Jesus finds no further evidence. In contrast, Li Chongfeng identifies the figure of the sculpture with a common, contemporary Buddhist figure Avalokitêsvara gazing at the moon in the water. There were monasteries or temples of Jingjiao in the confines of the Tang empire. The establishment of the Jingjiao temple was in accord with the rise and decline of the empire in different periods. The Xi'an inscription and other documents of local histories such as Liangjing xinji 兩京新記 and Chang'an Zhi 長安志 record the construction of Jingjiao temples at two imperial capital, Chang'an and Luoyang, and other prefectures. Chinese documents also report that Peroz III, son of the last Sasanian King of Kings of Iran Yazdegerd III, petitioned the Chinese emperor for permission to build a Persian temple, which has recognized as a Jingjiao temple. The Jingjiao temple was originally called 'Bosi-si' (Persian temple, 波斯寺), which was changed into 'Daqin-si' (Roman? temple, 大秦寺) under the edict of 745. The establishment of the Jingjiao temple was in accord with the rise and decline of the Tang empire in different periods. The Xi'an inscription and other documents of local histories such as Chang'an Zhi 長安志 record the construction of Jingjiao temples at two imperial capital, Chang'an and Luoyang, and other prefectures. The Jingjiao temple was originally called 'Bosi Si' (Persian temple, 波斯寺), which was changed into 'DaQin si' (Roman? temple, 大秦寺) under the edict of 745.

Reference: Wushu Lin. Did The Ta-ch'in Monastery in Chou-chih belong to the Nestorianism during the Tang Dynasty?.

Reference: Martin Palmer, Eva Wong. The Jesus Sutras. Wellspring/Ballantine. isbn: 9780345434241. p.11-38

Reference: Chongfeng Li. A Nestorian Pagoda at Zhouzhi, Shaanxi.

Reference: Da Xiang. Tangdai Chang'an yu xiyu wenming. Shijiazhuang: Hebei jiaoyu chubanshe. p.105-111

Reference: F. Drake S.. Nestorian Monasteries of the T'ang Dynasty. Monumenta serica, 2(1) p.293-340

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ In the average settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Size of largest single religious monument, square meters:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– Field doesn't know

↳ In the largest settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– Field doesn't know

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Tombs:

– Yes

Notes: Entombed epitaphs, or 'muzhiming', of a Sogdian official of Tang China, Hua Xian, and of his wife, the Lady An, were unearthed at Luoyang in 2010. Terminological connections with other Jingjiao documents confirm the identity of epitaphs.

Reference: Li Tang, Dietmar W. Winkler. Winds of Jingjiao. LIT Verlag Münster. isbn: 9783643907547. p.27-40

Reference: Morrow Kenneth T. Negotiating Belonging: The Church of the East's Contested Identity in Tang China. The University of Texas at Dallas. p.108-146

Reference: Yangguang Mao. Luoyang xin chutu tangdai jingjiaotu huaxian jiqi qi anshi muzhi chutan [A Study on the Epigraph of Nestorian Hua Xian and His Wife Ann of Tang Dynasty from Luoyang]. The Western Regions Studies, -2(2)

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Cemeteries:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Temples:

– Yes

Notes: The Xi'an inscription and other Chinese official documents report that the second emperor of Tang, Li Shimin, established a temple for Aluoben at Yining Fang in Chang'an.

Reference: Leslie Donald Daniel. Persian Temples in T'ang China. Monumenta serica, 35(1)

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Altars:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Devotional markers:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated using visible objects or structures]:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Other type of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes [specify]: Pagoda

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is iconography present:

– Yes

Notes: Scholars like Ken Parry have argued that iconography played a significant part in the Church of the East's Eastward expansion in Central Asia and China. The Syriac tradition had a long history of symbolic image-making before the rise of Islam in the 7th century. East Syriac Christians were not iconoclasts. The Xi'an inscription reproduces the edict issued in 638 by Emperor Taizong, which says that the Daqin priest Aluoben brought with him "scriptures and images" (jing xiang 經像) and presented them at the capital Chang'an. This is an early literary witness to the use of images in Jingjiao. In a recent article, R. Todd Godwin argued that East Syriac/Jingjiao Christians who erected the Xi'an stele had a culture of religious images and the mention of images in the Xi'an inscription was set against the development of esoteric Buddhism across empires of the Silk Roads (such as Tibet and Tang China) and the iconoclasm controversy in Byzantine Empire. The best recognizable icon of

Jingjiao is the cross on the Xi'an stele. It is a pearl cross, which has arms terminating in three pearls. This type of cross is representative of the church of the East. A similar shape of the cross can be found in Iraq. The pearl cross on the Xi'an stele is mounted on a lotus flower, which suggests the influence of Buddhist iconography, and an auspicious cloud design. The middle pearl on the top arm of the cross is surrounded by a flame. Moreover, on some headstones that were discovered in Quanzhou, which however have been dated to the Yuan dynasty (1268-1368), the cross is also supported on a lotus blossom or a bunch of flowers and a cloud design, which is reminiscent of the cross on the Xi'an stele. On the Luoyang pillar dedicated to the deceased Lady An, not just crosses but also flying angels, which look like apsaras, heavenly beings of the Buddhist tradition, can be found. Each cross is accompanied by two apsara-like figures. The pearl cross can also be found in a drawing of a horseman from the Christian at Qocho, which is dated to the late 9th century. Another painting also found at Qocho shows the event of Palm Sunday. In addition, a painting drawn on a silk hanging, discovered at Dunhuang by Aurel Stein in 1908, depicts a bodhisattva-like figure with 'the read moustache and wispy beard'. But the cross is apparently shown in the picture. Both Buddhist and Christian elements are present in Jingjiao's iconography.

Reference: R. Godwin Todd. Sacred Sovereigns across the Silk Road: The Church of the East's Gift of Buddhist-Christian Icons to the Chinese. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1353/bcs.2018.0019>. p.203-216

Reference: Ken Parry. Images in the Church of the East: the evidence from Central Asia and China. *Bulletin of the John Rylands Library*, 78(3) p.143-162

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: Religious Specialists Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

– Some public spaces

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: Religious Specialists Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: Religious Specialists Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Eyes (stylized or not):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: Religious Specialists Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic):

– No

Notes: The image of dragons is inscribed on the top of the Xi'an stele.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract symbol):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Portrayals of afterlife:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Humans:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Other features of iconography:

– Yes

Notes: The lotus, auspicious clouds, and dragons, which are typically Chinese ornaments, are incorporated into Jingjiao's iconography.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– I don't know

Are pilgrimages present:

– I don't know

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Notes: The distinction between soul (hunpo 魂魄) and body/flesh (roushen 肉身) is a significant topic that the Discourse on the One God articulates. For instance, the immortality of the soul is explained in the text: the soul does not need clothes and food. However, this does not mean the uselessness of the body, which has five senses and is the starting point of perception.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

– Yes

↳ Other spirit-body relationship:

– Yes [specify]: Shenshi 神識 (consciousness) is an important concept in the Discourse on the One God.

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: There is a distinction between this world (ci tianxia 此天下) and the other world (bi tianxia 彼天下) in the Discourse of the One God when the immortality of the soul is explained.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined “above” space:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined “below” space:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined horizontal space:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Afterlife located in "other" space:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Notes: Although many Buddhist terminologies are employed in Jingjiao's documents, it seems that the idea of reincarnation does not have a strong influence on these texts.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are grave goods present:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

Notes: There are many tomb epitaphs that, as Chinese scholars such as Rong Xinjiang and Ge Chengyong argue, belong to Jingjiao Christians. Most of these inscriptions were found in Chang'an and Luoyang. One of the most important archaeological discoveries is the inscription of the Luoyang pillar found in 2006. This inscription includes the text of the Book of Proclamation of the highest Origin of Origins.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ As cenotaphs:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ In cemetery:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Other formal burial type:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Notes: Introducing a supreme high God is one of the fundamental tasks of Jingjiao as a Christian religion. Firstly, naming the Only God in the Christian religion is an essential aspect of Christian missions, especially in the initiation period. There are mainly three approaches to naming the divine: transliteration, employing existing terminology, and neologism. Aluohe 阿羅訶 is the transliterated version of the Syriac term for God, 'alāhā. Tianzun 天尊, the Heavenly Worthy, is a term borrowed from the Daoist or Buddhist tradition. Yishen 一神, the One God, seems to be a neologism. Three approaches bring about three underlying, theological implications. The beginning parts of both of the two documents attributed to Aluoben primarily deal with the doctrine of God. The Book of Jesus Messiah stresses the invisibility of the Heavenly God. Moreover, both documents expound on God as the Creator. The Xi'an inscription ascribed to Jingjing states that God is the Creator with the overtones of Daoist metaphysics. Besides the inscription, the trinitarian shape of the Godhead is the central message.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– Yes

Notes: Jesus Christ is the second person of the Triune God. The humanity of Jesus Christ is a significant aspect of Jingjiao's teaching.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– Yes

Notes: As mentioned previously, the divine name "tianzun", which means the heavenly worthy, indicates this aspect.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– No

Notes: Some Chinese characters, such as *huang* 皇 (sovereign), *wang* 王 (king), *sheng* 聖 (holy), which were used to describe the monarch, are applied to characterizing the Triune God. The use of this term is to emphasize the sovereignty of the One God in such as worship. However, it should be noted that Jingjiao Christians do maintain the distinction between the emperor and the One God.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:

– Yes [specify]: Inviomnipotence, omniscience.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample

region:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite
(common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite
(common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite
(common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite
(common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite
(common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite
(common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite
(common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common
people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god can reward:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite
(common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god can punish:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite
(common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common
people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common
people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:

– No

Notes: Worshipping other supernatural beings in most cases is considered idolatry in the Christian religion. Opposing idolatry is an important topic in Aluoben's two documents. However, venerating angelic beings is legitimate in some cases.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite
(common people, general populace)

↳ In trance possession:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite
(common people, general populace)

↳ Through divination practices:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite
(common people, general populace)

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite
(common people, general populace)

↳ Only through monarch

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite
(common people, general populace)

↳ Other form of communication with living:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite
(common people, general populace)

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people,

general populace)

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

Notes: There are some references to angelic and demonic beings in the Book of Jesus Messiah as well as the Discourse on the One God. In particular, Buddhist terms such as "aluohan" (阿羅漢, arhat), "fo" (佛, Buddha), "e'mo" (惡魔, demons), "yecha" (夜叉, yakṣa) are employed in different passages. Besides, on the Luoyang pillar, each cross is flanked by images like apsaras (flying celestials) in Buddhism on either side.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

↳ Non-human supernatural beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have other knowledge of this world:

– I don't know

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:

– No

Notes: Christology is a theological theme dealing with the humanity and divinity of Jesus Christ. In terms of its theological roots, Jingjiao upheld dyophysitism, which insists on two natures of Jesus Christ. This is a Christology of the Antiochene school. Furthermore, the theology of "mixture" is the point that Nestorius and other Antiochene theologians opposed.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: In the Book of Jesus Messiah and the Discourse on the One God, heavenly beings and evil beings as described in Buddhist sutras are incorporated into the worldview of Jingjiao. For instance, the beginning of the Book of Jesus Messiah describes the supreme God, the Heavenly Worthy (tianzun), as a wind-like being, which cannot be seen by "non-human beings, Buddhas, devas and arhats". This implies a hierarchic system of supernatural beings.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Organized by kinship based on a family model:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Organized hierarchically:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Power of beings is domain specific:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Other organization for pantheon:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

Notes: In the Book of Jesus Messiah and the Discourse on the One God, the Buddhist discourse of retribution and merits (gongde 功德) is integrated into the arguments. Human beings are taught not to do evil deeds and to think about retribution for good or evil deeds, which are "the fruits of karma" (yebao 業報 or guobao 果報). The Only God as the Creator is the overseer of the process.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously "moral" or "ethical" norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

Notes: Good deeds are highly encouraged in Aluoben documents. An incomplete version of the Ten Commandments is introduced as ethical teachings. Caring for the weak, the needy, the sick, the poor (children) is taught in the Book of Jesus Messiah.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Supernatural beings care about taboos:

– Yes

Food:

– I don't know

Sacred space(s):

– I don't know

Sacred object(s):

– Yes

Supernatural beings care about other:

– I don't know

Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Adultery:

– Yes

Notes: This is one commandment of the Ten Commandments that is translated in the Book of Jesus Messiah.

↳ Incest:

– Yes

↳ Other sexual practices:

– I don't know

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:

– Yes

Notes: One of the Ten Commandment, "You shall not bear false witness against your neighbour [or other]", is included.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people,

general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:

– Yes

Notes: The concept of family reverence (xiao 孝) is incorporated into ethical teachings in the Book of Jesus Messiah.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people,

general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:

– Yes

Notes: Most of the texts that are ascribed to Jingjing are ritualistic.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:

– Yes

Notes: Verses of the "Great Commission" in Matthew 28 are translated as a part of the life of Jesus Christ in the Discourse on the One God.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Done only by high god:

– Yes

Notes: Idolatry is regarded as the temptation of the Devil, which results in the fall of humans who worship the Devil. Texts like the Discourse on the One God claim that the punishment comes after the acts of idolatry. Falling into hell is a warning, as stated in the text. The One God is announced as the one who judges.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– No

Notes: As mentioned previously, the Buddhist terminology of karma in Chinese is employed. However, there are no strong elements of the cause-effect principle as shown in the Buddhist teachings. God is the one who monitor and judge. Besides, the incarnate Messiah is the judge.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Done by other entities or through other means [specify]

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

Notes: The ritual aspect is one of the focuses in both the Book of Jesus Messiah and the Discourse on the One God. Worshipping the One God and Jesus Christ is regarded as good deeds that bring about blessings. On contrary, idolatry brings about spiritual punishments, such as falling into hell.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

people, general populace)

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Done randomly:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Other [specify]

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: "Diyu" 地獄, literally meaning "earth-prison", is originally a Buddhist term for hell. This concept is adopted in Jingjiao documents to illustrate the afterlife punishments.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural punishments in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– Yes

Notes: As the Discourse on the One God explains, the punishment in hell includes suffering under the big fire which burns without end.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as an inferior life form:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in an inferior realm:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Other [specify]

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– No

Notes: Jingjiao's texts seem to focus on supernatural punishments in the afterlife rather than in this lifetime.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

Notes: Aluoben documents highlight the benefits of worshipping the One God or the Heavenly Worthy and Jesus Messiah. The correct way of worshipping and honoring God brings about eternal happiness in paradise as well as blessings in this lifetime.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Done only by high god:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Done randomly:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural rewards in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: For example, "all sins are forgiven."

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of mild sensory pleasure:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory pleasure:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of eternal happiness:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as a superior life form:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in a superior realm:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Other [specify]

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:

– Yes

Notes: The Book on Attaining Mysterious Serenity and Joy emphasizes aspects of rewards bestowed out in this lifetime as the effects of this book.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Supernatural rewards in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

Reference: Li Tang. *A Study of the History of Nestorian Christianity in China and Its Literature in Chinese: Together with a New English Translation of the Dunhuang Nestorian Documents*. Peter Lang. p.188-199

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Reward in this life consists of good luck:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Reward in this life consists of political success or power:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Reward in this life consists of success in battle:

– No

Notes: However, the *Book on Attaining Mysterious Serenity and Joy* analogically tells of one benefit of practicing Jingjiao in this regard: Only this religion of Jing [Jingjiao] is the supreme law of success. It can protect all creatures from the thief of worries and troubles, like the armor and weaponry which protects the soldier's body."

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Reward in this life consists of peace or social stability:

– Yes

Notes: The *Book on Attaining Mysterious Serenity and Joy* says, "You disciples and all other listeners, go into the world and carry out my teachings. Then you can help the kings to protect their borders."

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Reward in this life consists of healthy crops or good weather:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Reward in this life consists of success on journeys:

– Yes

Notes: The Book on Attaining Mysterious Serenity and Joy says, "When people believe in love and practice this religion ... they will have no worry about difficulties when the road is bright. They will not encounter catastrophe when the road is dark."

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure:

– Yes

Notes: The Book on Attaining Mysterious Serenity and Joy says, "If you men and women follow my words and practice the supreme law industriously; meditate on the law day and night, then you shall stay away from all pollution and have the real nature of purity and peace. You shall have clear and complete wisdom, that is to know that this person shall be saved"

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants:

– Yes

Notes: The Book on Attaining Mysterious Serenity and Joy says, "If you want no lack of successors (of this teaching), you should preach about this teaching so that people will rejoice in it and sustain it. They shall read and recite the teaching and continue to observe it. These people should know that their ancestors, not only one or two generations, but all have been connected with the good cause. Due to the good roots accumulated by their former generations in the past, there have developed respectful teachings in our religion and thus blessings being received and wishes of joy cherished."

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Other [specify]

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– Yes

Notes: The belief in Jesus Christ is an essential part of the Church of the East as a form of the Christian religion. From the Western point of view (including Latin West and Greek East), the Church of the East has been regarded as a heresy of Nestorianism in terms of Christology, though a few patristic scholars such as James Franklin Bethune-Baker, Aloys Grillmeier, and Robert Victor Sellers have pointed out that Nestorianism in the Western eyes is different from the real teaching of Nestorius. The teaching of Nestorius is not a theology of "two sons", meaning that the humanity and the divinity of Jesus Christ are separate. On the basis of the Christological articulation, Sebastian Brock argued that the Church of the East is "Theodoran" rather than "Nestorian". The term "Theodoran" derives from the name of Theodore of Mopsuestia, whose Christological language shaped the Antiochene Christology, which was inherited by the Church of the East. In brief, Theodore emphasizes the doctrine of "two natures" of Jesus Christ as well as the unity of these two natures in "prosopon" (person or "persona" in Latin). The belief in Jesus Christ is strongly present in Jingjiao's documents in various ways. First, Mishihe 彌施/師訶 is a transliteration from the Syriac term for "messiah". This title, which is used in almost all Jingjiao's documents, becomes a name for Jesus. Varied titles ascribed to Christ were employed and invented in texts such as the Chinese version of Gloria in Excelsis Deo. The World-honored One (shizun 世尊), an epithet of the Buddha, was employed especially in the third part of the Discourse of the One God. The description of Mishihe is also placed in the trinitarian shape. Mishihe is also worshipped as the second

person of the Triune God in a liturgical text.

Reference: Robert V. Sellers. Two Ancient Christologies. isbn: 9780404623944.

Reference: Aloys Grillmeier. Christ in Christian Tradition. Westminster John Knox Press. isbn: 9780664223014.

Reference: J.F. Bethune-Baker. Nestorius and His Teachings. Wipf and Stock Publishers. isbn: 9781579101947.

Reference: Sebastian P. Brock. Fire from Heaven. Ashgate Publishing, Ltd.. isbn: 9780754659082. fig.1-14

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Is the messiah's whereabouts or time of coming known?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Is the messiah's purpose known:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Messiah is a political figure who restores political rule:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Messiah is a priestly figure who restores religious traditions:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Other purpose:

– Yes [specify]: Saving the humanity.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is an eschatology present:

– Yes

Notes: There are teachings about the afterlife in the Discourse of the One God when the author talks about the soul benefiting from worshipping God in the afterlife. However, the second coming of Jesus Christ is not explicitly mentioned.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Eschaton in this lifetime:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Eschaton at specified time in future:

– No

↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in near future:

– Yes

↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in distant future:

– No

↳ Eschaton at some other time:

– No

↳ Adherents need to perform specific tasks to bring about World's end:

– I don't know

↳ Divine judgment event:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people,

general populace)

↳ Restoration of the world:
– I don't know

↳ Start of a new temporal cycle:
– No

↳ Establishment of a new political system:
– No

↳ Establishment of a new religious system:
– No

↳ Will anyone survive the eschaton:
– I don't know

Notes: The Discourse on the One God says, "If the world is going to be extinguished or reborn after an aeon, the soul will return to the five aggregates, naturally in its completion without need to seek clothing for food, always maintains in happiness, playing with supernatural power and does not support a materialized body." This passage indicates a general scene of the eschaton. But few surviving texts of Jingjiao mention other eschatological ideas such as the new heaven and the new earth.

Reference: Victor Manuel Aguilar Sanchez. *Corpus Nestorianum Sinicum: Thus Have I Heard on the Listening of Mishihe (the Messiah) and "Discourse on the One-God". A Theological Approach with a Proposed Reading Structure and Translation.* Pontificia Univ. Gregoriana. isbn: 9788878394384. p.691

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– No

Notes: As a minority, the community of Jingjiao Christians in a way conformed to the social norms prescribed by pre-existing traditions such as Confucianism. For instance, in the Book of Jesus Messiah, honoring parents is treated as equal to "family reverence" (xiao 孝) that is an important theme in Confucianism. Honoring and serving the emperor are also emphasized in the same text. However, this does not mean that Jingjiao did not have norms that prescribed its members. One example is the attitude toward slavery, which was normal in the Tang society. As the Xi'an inscription highlights this aspect, "They do not keep slaves; all men, of high status and low, are equal."

Reference: Lance Eccles, Samuel Lieu *Stele on the diffusion of the Luminous Religion of Da Qin (Rome) in the Middle Kingdom*

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– I don't know

Notes: Ethical teachings form an important part of the two documents ascribed to Aluoben.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: In the 2nd and 3rd centuries, celibacy seemed to be a requirement for baptism, which is based on rigid ecclesiology with strong eschatology. The Acts of Thomas teaches that "the fundamental doctrine that Christian life is unobtainable without the price of virginity." This strict requirement of membership gradually disappeared partially because of the expansion of the Church in Mesopotamia. It was recognized that married Christians belong to the church. In addition, among the group of bnay/bnāt qyāmā, celibacy is not considered a requirement for inclusion, as stated in Aphrahat's Six Demonstration. In later periods, celibacy is by and large limited to monasteries. The Synod of Seleucia-Ctesiphon under Aqaq's leadership in 486 took measures to restrain the rigorous form of asceticism outside of monasteries and to make marriage the preferred status for all clergy, including bishops. Thus, it is believed that this rule also applied to Jingjiao's clergy in the Tang empire.

Reference: Sebastian P. Brock. Gorgias Encyclopedic Dictionary of the Syriac Heritage. Gorgias Press LLC. isbn: 9781593337148. p.27

Reference: Arthur Vööbus. Celibacy, a requirement for admission to baptism in the early Syrian Church. Stockholm: Estonian Theological Society.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Notes: But in some circles of Syriac Christianity, the radical means of castration was fairly popular. There is a record of this practice in the Apostolic Constitutions, a text originating in Syria in the 4th century. However, this practice was strongly opposed in the mainline ecclesiastical tradition, as stated in the canons of Rabbula.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– Yes

Notes: It is a popular form of asceticism, especially among monastics. The Xi'an stele introduces the fasting among monks: "[T]hey abstain from meat to purify their minds and develop themselves."

Reference: Lance Eccles, Samuel Lieu. Stele on the diffusion of the Luminous Religion of Da Qin (Rome) in the Middle Kingdom.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– Yes

Notes: Poverty is another requirement in Syriac monasticism. The Xi'an inscription says that "They [monks] do not accumulate possessions, but demonstrate their frugality by handing over their possessions to others. "

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

To other in-group members:

– Yes

To out-groups:

– Yes

Destroyed:

– No

↳ Other:

– I don't know

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Notes: Many of Jingjiao's documents are liturgical, which indicates that the regular activities of church service. The Xi'an inscription also says that "At the seventh hour of the day a ceremony of hymns (psalms?) is performed for the benefit of the living and the dead. Once in every seven days, they cleanse their hearts and return to a state of purity."

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Notes: The ethical teachings are a significant part of the Book of Jesus Messiah and the Discourse of the One God. Some teachings are drawn and translated from the Gospel of Matthew.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale "ceremonies" and "festivals."

– Yes

Notes: But celebrations of important festivals like Easter are not found in the surviving texts of Jingjiao.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does participation entail synchronic practices:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is there use of intoxicants:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– I don't know

Notes: Titles like "brothers (and sisters)" in the Bible seem not to be found in the texts of Jingjiao.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– An empire

Notes: The Church of the East was politically connected with the Persian court since the Synod of Isaac in 410 when Yazdegerd I maintained cordial relations with the Eastern Roman Empire through the intermediate role of East Syrians. Since then, the Church of the East played a continued role in imperial politics in Persia even after the Muslim conquest. With the fall of the Persian empire, the royal family was exiled and took refuge in the Tang empire. It has been argued that East Syriac Christians in the Tang court 'very likely played a role in strengthening Sasanian restoration hopes'. The Tang empire (617-907) was one of the most cosmopolitan periods in Chinese history. In 630, as the Tang army defeated the Eastern Turks, Emperor Taizong was titled as Tengeri Qaghan 天可汗. This enabled transportation and communication between the Chinese empire and the Western Regions (Xiyu 西域). With the first missionary, Aluoben as the pioneer, the Church of the East was granted an official place between 638 and 845. As such, East Syriac Christians, especially church elites, as intermediaries were involved in inter-imperial relations. They played an active role in maintaining diplomatic and cultural contacts with Central Asia and Tang China.

Reference: R. Todd Godwin. *Persian Christians at the Chinese Court*. Bloomsbury Publishing. isbn: 9781786723161. p.26

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Yes

Notes: The Church of the East played an educational role among its adherents by establishing the School of Nisibis and other monastic schools. The School of Nisibis inherited the legacy of the School of Edessa, which was a base of the Antiochene School. The pedagogical role of these big and small schools was essential for training the clergy, the monastic community, and, possibly, the laypeople and for maintaining the theological tradition and innovation. The relics of monasteries have been discovered in Northwest China. But the specific educational role has not been identified. The degree to which monasteries or temples of Jingjiao functioned as an educational institute for its adherent is uncertain, given the lack of obvious evidence.

Reference: Adam H. Becker. *Fear of God and the Beginning of Wisdom*. University of Pennsylvania Press. isbn: 9780812201208.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is formal education restricted to religious professionals:

– No

Is such education open to both males and females:

– I don't know

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Notes: There is an ecclesiastical hierarchy in the Church of the East, where Catholicos is the head. Besides, it is said that there was a metropolitan responsible for China. On the Xi'an stele, Catholicos Henanisho's Syriac name and its Chinese transliteration are noted at the end of the inscription. Jingjing/Adam, the author of the inscription, is a chorepiscopus of China.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Notes: As noted previously, the Church of the East's elites interacted with imperial courts in Persia, Central Asia, as well as Tang China. According to the Xi'an stele and some other archaeological discoveries (like entombed epitaphs), some Jingjiao Christians were appointed as officials in the Tang government. For example, the donor of the Xi'an stele took a role in the Tang army, especially during the period of the An Lushan Rebellion (755- 763). Rong Xinjiang from Peking University identified the Persian Li Su 李素 with a name appearing on the Xi'an stele. Li Su was from the Sasanian royal family and his grandfather came to China as a hostage ("zhizi", 質子). He himself took an official position as an astronomer at the Tang court. In addition, Ge Chengyong discovered that a son of Mi Jifen 米繼芬 was a monk at the Jingjiao temple/monastery. Mi was also a descendent of a foreign hostage and held a high military title in Tang.

Reference: R. Todd Godwin. *Persian Christians at the Chinese Court*. Bloomsbury Publishing. isbn: 9781786723161.

Reference: Chengyong Ge , Matteo Nicolini-Zani. *The Christian Faith of a Sogdian Family in Chang'an during the Tang Dynasty*. p.181-196

Reference: Xingjiang Rong. *Yige Rushi Tangchao de Bosi Jingjiao Jiazuo*. (Xingjiang Rong), *Zhongguo Zhongguo Yu Wailai Wenming*. Beijing: Sanlian chubanshe. p.238-257

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: Although it was not the judicial system in the modern sense, the imperial power represented by the Tang emperor was overwhelming even in the religious sphere.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: A typical example would be the Huichang Persecution of Buddhism in 845 when Jingjiao Christians were persecuted along with Buddhists and Zoroastrians.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– I don't know

Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– I don't know

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– I don't know

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: According to the Xi'an inscription and several epitaphs discovered at Chang'an, the Church of the East's elites undertook the military role in the Tang army, as mentioned previously.

Reference: R. Todd Godwin. *Persian Christians at the Chinese Court*. Bloomsbury Publishing. isbn: 9781786723161.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– Yes

Notes: Almost from its earliest periods, the Syriac language is deeply connected with Christian literature. Classical Syriac is not just used in the liturgical setting but also written and spoken among people in the Syriac tradition. Syriac words in the Estrangelo form are engraved on the Xi'an stele. Syriac can also be found in various inscriptions scattered in China. In Jingjiao documents, transliterations from Syriac can be found. For instance, "mishihe" 彌施訶 is transliterated from the Syriac term for "messiah".

Reference: Sebastian P. Brock. *An Introduction to Syriac Studies*. Gorgias Press. isbn: 9781463207137.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

↳ Is use of this distinct written language confined to religious professionals:

– Yes

Notes: It is certain that the clergy like Jingjing was familiar with Syriac. It is unlikely that the laity who were Persian, Sogdian, or Turkish people could have access to Syriac which was not their mother tongue.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: It is highly likely that Jingjiao Christians whose ancestors migrated from Persian or Central Asia were exposed to the Chinese language. This could be testified by the use of the Chinese language in Jingjiao's surviving documents. There were theological treatises as well as liturgical texts.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Yes

Notes: A dozen or so fragments found at Turfan in Northwest China are calendrical tables determining dates in the liturgical calendar. In addition, there is information about the date of erecting the stele: "Set up in the great T'ang, Chien-chung, second year, the solar period being in tso-o, the t'ai-tsou [太歲] month, seventh day, the great yao-sên-wên [耀森文] day." Alexander Wylie identified Yao-sen-wen with the Persian "yaksambah" (first day). This line indicates the calendar used and maintained by Jingjiao Christians.

Reference: A. C. Moule. *Christians in China Before the Year 1550*. isbn: 9780879688653. p.47

Reference: Jonathan Ben-Dov, Wayne Horowitz, John M. Steele. *Living the Lunar Calendar*. Oxbow Books Limited. isbn: 9781842174814. p.269-296

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: In Jingjiao documents, such as the inscriptions of the Xi'an stele and the Luoyang pillar, the Chinese calendar of the regnal year was also adopted by Jingjiao Christians. For example, it is said that Aluoben came to Chang'an in the ninth year of Zhenguang (貞觀九祀/年), which is the year of 635 in the common era.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group

in question:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

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